

Designing at 1:1 Scale on Wall-Sized Displays Using Existing UI Design Tools

Annex 1

Second user study documents: prototyping at 1:1 scale on WSD with Figma

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Introduction

This document is an annex to the paper “Designing at 1:1 Scale *on* Wall-Sized Displays Using Existing UI Design Tools” written by Lou Schwartz, Mohammad Ghoniem, Valérie Maquil, Adrien Coppens, and Johannes Hermen.

This document contains documents used to conduct the first user study about prototyping at 1:1 scale on WSD with Figma and its results. It is composed as follows:

1. The technical protocol.
2. Discussion guide: the guide for the facilitator to present the experimentation to participants and to collect their consent.
3. Task description: the mockup to reproduce during the user study.
4. Mockups made by the participant: the result produced by the participant for each condition.

1. Technical protocol

1.1. Before each session

For the WSD-IA

1. Switch on the screens
2. Switch on the WSD-IA computer
3. Switch on the OBS computer (that manage the observation system)
4. Launch the user study environment (button XP Figma)
5. Log in to Figma
6. For the touch, position the Chrome Window at the middle on only 8 screens.
7. If WSD-IA, place the table at the center with the physical keyboard and the paper mockup on
8. Load the tablet if necessary

For the WSD-VW

1. Let the technician start the WSD-VW
2. Open Chrome and load Figma
3. Log in to Figma
4. Position tables and chairs in initial position
5. Position the video cameras
6. Load the tablet if necessary

Welcome participant

For the first session, see the discussion guide bellow

1.2. During the session

1. Open the corresponding project on the WSD
 - a. If TABLET then, open the same project on the tablet that on the WSD
2. Start recording
3. Let the participant execute the task

4. Stop recording
5. Screen shot of the result (FN+BACK)
 - a. If TABLET, then screenshot of the result on the tablet

2. Discussion guide

2.1. Welcome

2.2. Project objective

This experiment is taking place as part of the PLAY project, which studies how to design on wall-sized displays.

2.1.Explanation of the purpose of the study

In this experiment, we ask you to reproduce the attached design using three interaction methods.

1. First, we will ask you to use the touch as much as possible and the keyboard if necessary.
2. Then, we will ask you to reproduce the same design using only the keyboard and the touchpad on the keyboard.
3. Finally, we will ask you to repeat the experiment, this time using the tablet to create the design.

We ask you to reproduce the design provided as exactly as possible.

The experiment for each means of interaction will last a maximum of 1h30.

At any time, you can interrupt the experiment if you feel discomfort or too much physical fatigue.

We ask you to explain your actions out loud.

During these experiments, you will be filmed by several cameras and recorded by a microphone.

2.2. Consent form signature

Before to start, I will ask you to read this information concerning your right about the management of your data and sign the consent form in 2 copies, one for you and one for us.

We will record the study by video and microphone and observe all your actions. Your data will be pseudonymised. And the capturing elements will be used for scientific dissemination.

If you have any questions, please ask them before you sign.

3. Task description

3.1. Interface to reproduce

Figure 1: overall view of the rendering on the immersive arena.

Figure 2: Print screen.

3.1.Close-up views

News

@RTLToday

● Luxembourg is in the middle of a new Omega wave. Latest projections from the Covid-19 Taskforce show that there will be a **peak** in September with 1200 new infections per day. Hospitalizations will reach up to 60 in normal care and up to 20 in ICU.

4:38 PM · Jul 28, 2024 · Twitter Web App

10k Retweets 8k Quote Tweets 899 Likes

@WHO

 BREAKING:
The WHO warns from a new variant of the coronavirus that seems to lead to more hospitalizations. It is more important than ever that you get your vaccination and booster as soon as possible #fight #COVID19.

**Omega Variant
spreading!**

4:50 PM · Jul 29, 2024 · Twitter Web App

104k Retweets 88k Quote Tweets 500k Likes

COVID Estimation

Here you can estimate hospital and ICU occupancy for the next three months. Move the sliders accordingly.

New infections per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

Hospital occupancy per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

ICU occupancy per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

COVID Data

These graphs show you the current COVID numbers (blue) as well as the estimated ones (red) for the next three months.

New Infections

Hospital occupancy Luxembourg

ICU occupancy

Hospital occupancy (your hospital)

ICU occupancy (your hospital)

Attendees

This Screen shows the list of current Attendees.

4. Mockups produced by the participant

4.1. WSD-IA, touch

4.2. WSD-IA, keyboard

4.3. WSD-IA, tablet

4.4. WSD-WV, keyboard

4.5. WSD-WV, tablet

4.6. WSD-WV, touch

